

NEW PROBABILISTIC MEASURES FOR ACCELERATING THE AUTOMATIC TEST PATTERN GENERATION ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

In order to approximate the signal controllabilities, this research introduces new probabilistic measures called "signal priorities," whose computation relies on the "minimum-value distributions" of fanout input variables of a digital circuit. The signal priorities serve the same purpose as do the signal controllabilities. That is, they are used to accelerate the automatic test pattern generation algorithm; however, their computation requires much less effort. This new method is formally defined and tested with several practical example circuits.

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this research is to seek a more efficient technique that would accelerate an existing Automatic Test Pattern Generation algorithm for detecting single stuck-at faults in digital circuits. The intent is to reduce the overall testing cost and produce high-quality input test patterns that would detect a high percentage of faults.

A number of Deterministic Automatic Test Pattern Generation (DATPG) algorithms have been developed over the years. Because of the increasing complexity of digital systems, current research activity has focused on the acceleration of the existing DATPG algorithms. With this in mind, the following investigates the progress that has been made so far.

One of the very first DATPG algorithms called "D-algorithm" was designed by Roth [1966]. The D-algorithm was considered a significant research work because it was formally proven to be a complete algorithm, which, for a given fault, guaranteed to find an input test pattern if one existed. The basic feature of the D-algorithm was that its fault processing started at the fault's location, and advanced toward the primary outputs and inputs of the circuit. However, for certain types of

combinational circuits, such a fault processing strategy of the D-algorithm became very inefficient due to an excessive number of backtrackings during the determination of the desired input test patterns. Such a problem made the D-algorithm potentially an exhaustive algorithm.

In 1981, an algorithm called "PODEM" (path-oriented decision making) was developed to overcome the deficiency of the D-algorithm [Goel 1981]. Instead of starting the fault processing at the fault's location, PODEM started at the primary inputs of the circuit and advanced toward the primary outputs of the circuit. PODEM also imposed several conditions for early termination of the search process whenever the fault's effect was found not observable.

By employing the above features, Goel showed that for certain types of combinational circuits, PODEM potentially could prevent the search for input test patterns from degenerating into an exhaustive process. Thus, the performance of PODEM was more efficient compared to that of the D-algorithm. However, PODEM still faced the same problem as did the D-algorithm for a more general class of combinational circuits.

Two years later, FAN (fanout-oriented test generation algorithm), developed by Fujiwara and Shimono [1983], introduced a new search strategy that further improved the performance of the test generation. Based on the fanout structure of the circuit, FAN's search mechanism performed on multiple paths in the circuit to speed up the fault processing. Upon meeting an internal fanout signal that was fed by a fanout-free sub-circuit and not accessible by the fault effect, FAN postponed the search process so that it could work on other tasks.

Efforts on accelerating the existing DATPG algorithms summarized so far have been concerned with how the search process in the DATPG could be guided, so that it would not degenerate into an exhaustive procedure. These search strategies were developed directly based on the topological analysis of the circuit. However, these

search strategies had a big drawback. That is, the analysis did not actually take into account the probabilistic distributions of signal lines. As a result, the test patterns found may not be valid due to their small probabilities of occurrences.

Nevertheless, there were other search acceleration techniques available. These techniques relied on probabilistic measures such as the "signal controllabilities" of the signal lines in the circuit. The signal controllability of a signal line is defined as the probability that the line is set to a specified value (0 or 1 in the binary logic system) when the input pattern is randomly applied to the circuit. Agrawal [1985] was one of the pioneers in promoting the probabilistic guidance for the search process in the DATPG. In his paper, titled "Probabilistically Guided Test Generation," Agrawal experimentally showed that the signal controllabilities guided the search process more efficiently than did the search strategy of PODEM.

The problem with the probabilistic approach mentioned above was that the computation of the exact signal controllabilities increased exponentially with the number of fanout input variables of the circuit. Research works such as [Savir et al. 1984, Seth et al. 1985, Chakravarty and Hunt III 1990] had shown ways to improve the efficiency aspect of the signal controllability computation, but the result was still far from being satisfactory. For example, very often, the controllability was severely underestimated by using the method proposed by Savir (see [Chakravarty and Hunt III 1990]). Also, the "Efficient Enumeration" method developed by Chakravarty and Hunt III relied heavily on redundant subcircuits which would not be intentionally designed in many cases.

In order to approximate the signal controllabilities as many other researchers have done, we will introduce new parameters called "signal priorities" that serve the same purpose as did the signal probabilities (i.e., guiding the test generation process), but their computation effort is reduced significantly.

The reduction mentioned above is achieved by employing the "minimum-value distributions" [Soong 1981] of the fanout input variables of the circuit. Based on these distributions, only those input test patterns that would contribute a significant weight to the computation of the signal controllability of a circuit line are enumerated; the other input test patterns are totally ignored in the process. As a result, the computation process is implicit (i.e., not exhaustive). The result of such a computation, for a given circuit line, is what we call the "signal priority."

By using the above implicit method, we will show that the amount of computation for the signal priority of a given line in a circuit is about half that of the exact signal controllability. For a large digital circuit with a large number of fanout input variables, such a reduction in the computation significantly accelerates the overall DATPG. Also, we will present a method for evaluating the

maximum difference between the 1-priority and the exact 1-controllability for any given signal in a circuit.

To demonstrate the computation and utility of the 1-priority, we conducted several simulations. One of the simulations involved a part of a real circuit that had been maintained at the Oklahoma City Air Logistics Center, Tinker Air Force Base. The results of the simulations consistently showed that the signal priority could be efficiently used to replace the traditional exact controllability to accelerate the test pattern generation process.

2. COMPUTATION OF EXACT CONTROLLABILITIES

For a fanout-free circuit, the computation of 1-controllabilities can be performed in linear time using simple probability expressions shown below.

a) An AND gate U with output g and N inputs (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_N):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Prob}\{\text{Output of U is 1}\} &= \text{Prob}\{U(g)=1\} \\ &= \text{Prob}\{X_1=1\} \times \dots \times \text{Prob}\{X_N=1\} \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

b) An OR gate U with output g and N inputs (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_N):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Prob}\{U(g)=1\} &= 1 - (1 - \text{Prob}\{X_1=1\}) \times \\ &\dots \times (1 - \text{Prob}\{X_N=1\}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

c) A NOT gate U with input i and output g:

$$\text{Prob}\{U(g)=1\} = 1 - \text{Prob}\{U(i)=0\} \quad (2.3)$$

d) XOR and XNOR gates:

The 1-controllability of the output of each of these gates is calculated in terms of the 1-controllabilities of the outputs of AND, OR, and NOT gates that implement the XOR or XNOR function.

For a circuit that has K fanout inputs F_1, F_2, \dots, F_K , the exact computation of the 1-controllability $\text{Prob}\{g=1\}$, where g is any signal line the circuit, requires an exhaustive enumeration of 2^K K-tuples. The $\text{Prob}\{g=1\}$ is defined as

$$\text{Prob}\{g=1\} = \sum_{i=1}^{2^K} \text{Prob}\{g=1\} \cap (H_i) \quad (2.4)$$

where H_i is the i^{th} K-tuple. Using the definition of the conditional probability, Equation 2.4 is rewritten as

$$\text{Prob}\{g=1\} = \sum_{i=1}^{2^K} \text{Prob}\{g=1 \mid H_i\} \times \text{Prob}\{H_i\} \quad (2.5)$$

where, for

$$v_s \in \{0, 1\}, s = 1 \dots K$$

one has

$$\text{Prob}\{H_i\} = \text{Prob}\{F_1=v_1 \cap \dots \cap F_K=v_K\}$$

or

$$\text{Prob}\{H_i\} = \text{Prob}\{F_1=v_1\} \times \dots \times \text{Prob}\{F_K=v_K\} \quad (2.6)$$

and the conditional term $\text{Prob}\{g=1 \mid H_i\}$ for each i can be computed directly using Equations 2.1-3.

For convenience in later discussion and computer simulations, the conditional and unconditional terms in Equation 2.5 are rewritten in a matrix notation. Let $C(1,g)$ denote a 1×2^K conditional 1-controllability matrix

whose elements correspond to the conditional terms in Equation 2.5. The matrix $C(1,g)$ is then defined as

$$C(1,g) = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Prob}\{g=1\} | H_1 \\ \text{Prob}\{g=1\} | H_2 \\ \vdots \\ \text{Prob}\{g=1\} | H_{2^k} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (2.7)$$

where $[\]^T$ denotes the matrix transpose operator, and H_i ($i = 1 \dots 2^k$) is the i^{th} K -tuple. As an example, $H_1 = (F_1 = 0, F_2 = 0, \dots, F_K = 0)$, $H_2 = (F_1 = 0, F_2 = 0, \dots, F_K = 1)$, etc..

Using Equation 2.7, the corresponding 1×2^k conditional 0-controllability matrix, $C(0,g)$, can be easily found by subtracting every elements of $C(1,g)$ from 1. Also, the conditional controllability matrix for the output of a logic gate with T inputs can be expressed in terms of its input conditional controllability matrices:

a) A T -input AND gate with output g :

$$C(1,g) = C(1, \text{input } 1) \otimes C(1, \text{input } 2) \otimes \dots \otimes C(1, \text{input } T) \quad (2.8)$$

where the symbol \otimes denotes array element-by-element multiplication. The \otimes operation is different from the usual linear algebraic matrix multiplication. For example, if array A and array B have the same dimensions, then $A \otimes B$ denotes the array whose elements are the products of the individual elements of A and B .

b) A T -input OR gate with output g :

$$C(0,g) = C(0, \text{input } 1) \otimes C(0, \text{input } 2) \otimes \dots \otimes C(0, \text{input } T) \quad (2.9)$$

c) A NOT gate with output g :

$$C(1,g) = C(0, \text{input}) \quad (2.10)$$

Let $H(F)$ be a $2^k \times 1$ fanout probability matrix, whose elements correspond to the unconditional terms in Equation 2.5. $H(F)$ is defined as

$$H(F) = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Prob}\{H_1\} \\ \text{Prob}\{H_2\} \\ \vdots \\ \text{Prob}\{H_{2^k}\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.11)$$

where $\text{Prob}\{H_i\}$ is specified in Equation 2.6. As an example, $\text{Prob}\{H_1\} = \text{Prob}\{F_1=0\} \times \text{Prob}\{F_2=0\} \times \dots \times \text{Prob}\{F_K=0\}$, and $\text{Prob}\{H_2\} = \text{Prob}\{F_1=0\} \times \text{Prob}\{F_2=0\} \times \dots \times \text{Prob}\{F_K=1\}$, etc..

By using Equations 2.7 and 2.11, the 1-controllability of any line g is

$$\text{Prob}\{g=1\} = C(1,g) * H(F) \quad (2.12)$$

where the symbol $*$ denotes the usual linear algebraic matrix multiplication.

3. DEVELOPMENT AND COMPUTATION OF SIGNAL PRIORITIES

There are two types of signal priorities: 0-priority and 1-priority. The definition and use of signal priorities are equivalent to those of signal controllabilities. That is, the priority of a signal is defined as the probability of

setting that signal to a specified value when an input pattern is randomly selected and applied to the circuit. When the 0-priority is higher than the 1-priority for a given signal line, it implies that the 0 value is more justifiable than is the 1 value, and vice versa.

As with controllabilities, the signal priorities are used to effectively guide the justification process so that the number of backtrackings is reduced. The development and computation of signal priorities are described in the following sections.

3.1 Minimum-value Distributions of Fanouts

Consider a digital circuit with K fanout inputs F_1, F_2, \dots, F_K , and a signal value $v \in \{0, 1\}$. Let M_v denote an event which is defined as

$$M_v = \text{Prob}\{\text{at least one } F_k = v\} \quad (3.1)$$

where $k = 1 \dots K$. For $v = 0$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Prob}\{M_0\} &= \text{Prob}\{\text{at least one } F_k = 0\} \\ &= \text{Prob}\{F_1 = 0 \cup \dots \cup F_K = 0\} \\ &= 1 - \text{Prob}\{F_1 = 1 \cap \dots \cap F_K = 1\} \\ &= 1 - [1 - \text{Prob}\{F_1 = 0\}] \times \\ &\quad \dots \times [1 - \text{Prob}\{F_K = 0\}] \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

where the signal controllabilities of F_k for all k are assumed to be independent. When the probability distributions of all F_k are identical, Equation 3.2 becomes

$$\text{Prob}\{M_0\} = 1 - [1 - \text{Prob}\{F_k = 0\}]^K \quad (3.3)$$

The corresponding expressions for $\text{Prob}\{M_1\}$ can be easily obtained by changing the 0's to 1's in each of the Equations 3.2 and 3.3. One has

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Prob}\{M_1\} &= 1 - [1 - \text{Prob}\{F_1 = 1\}] \times \\ &\quad \dots \times [1 - \text{Prob}\{F_K = 1\}] \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

and

$$\text{Prob}\{M_1\} = 1 - [1 - \text{Prob}\{F_k = 1\}]^K \quad (3.5)$$

when the probability distributions of F_k are identical. The probability distributions of M_v are termed the minimum-value distributions [Soong 1981] of fanout variables.

As will be shown later, the probability distribution of M_v plays a critical role in the computation of the signal priorities. For now, note that when $\text{Prob}\{M_0\} > \text{Prob}\{M_1\}$, it means that, among the 2^k K -tuples, the probabilities of occurrences of the K -tuples that have a majority of 0 signals are generally larger than those of the K -tuples that have a majority of 1 signals. On the other hand, when $\text{Prob}\{M_0\} < \text{Prob}\{M_1\}$, the occurrences of the 1-majority K -tuples are generally more frequent than are those of the 0-majority K -tuples. For example, suppose that a circuit has 3 fanout inputs F_1, F_2 , and F_3 . When $\text{Prob}\{M_0\} < \text{Prob}\{M_1\}$ (or $\text{Prob}\{M_0\} > \text{Prob}\{M_1\}$), then

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 0 \text{ and } F_2 = 0 \text{ and } F_3 = 0\} \\ &\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 0 \text{ and } F_2 = 0 \text{ and } F_3 = 1\} \\ &\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 0 \text{ and } F_2 = 1 \text{ and } F_3 = 0\} \\ &\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 1 \text{ and } F_2 = 0 \text{ and } F_3 = 0\} \end{aligned}$$

are generally smaller (or larger) than

$$\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 1 \text{ and } F_2 = 1 \text{ and } F_3 = 1\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 1 \text{ and } F_2 = 1 \text{ and } F_3 = 0\} \\ &\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 1 \text{ and } F_2 = 0 \text{ and } F_3 = 1\} \\ &\text{Prob}\{F_1 = 0 \text{ and } F_2 = 1 \text{ and } F_3 = 1\} \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Computation of Signal Priorities

When $\text{Prob}\{M_1\} > \text{Prob}\{M_0\}$, the quantities $\text{Prob}\{H_i\}$ corresponding to the 0-majority fanout combinations will be smaller compared to those of the 1-majority fanout combinations. In such a case, one can simply ignore the rows of $H(F)$ that correspond to the small $\text{Prob}\{H_i\}$, and the value of $\text{Prob}\{g\}$ calculated from Equation 2.12 will not be significantly affected. This is especially true when the absolute difference between $\text{Prob}\{M_1\}$ and $\text{Prob}\{M_0\}$ is large. To illustrate this point, two calculations are performed on an arbitrary digital circuit that has 5 fanout input variables whose signal probabilities are randomly generated (the internal structure of this circuit is not relevant at this point). Also, for simplicity, assume that each of the elements of the matrix $C(1,g)$ is equal to 1.

a) The signal probabilities of the fanout inputs are generated such that $\text{Prob}\{M_1\} > \text{Prob}\{M_0\}$ (see Figure 1). In this case, the probabilities of occurrences of input combinations $H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5, H_6, H_7, H_8, H_9, H_{10}, H_{11}, H_{13}, H_{17}, H_{18}, H_{19}, H_{21},$ and H_{25} are generally small compared to the others. The probabilities of these tuples can be ignored in the computation of Equation 2.12 since their sum contributes about 16% to the computation.

b) The signal probabilities of the fanout inputs are generated such that $\text{Prob}\{M_0\} > \text{Prob}\{M_1\}$ (see Figure 2). In this case, the probabilities of occurrences of the input combinations $H_8, H_{12}, H_{14}, H_{15}, H_{16}, H_{20}, H_{22}, H_{23}, H_{24}, H_{26}, H_{27}, H_{28}, H_{29}, H_{30}, H_{31},$ and H_{32} are generally small compared to the others. The probabilities of these tuples can be ignored in the computation of Equation 2.12 since their sum contributes about 16% to the computation.

Obviously, the larger the difference between $\text{Prob}\{M_0\}$ and $\text{Prob}\{M_1\}$, the more accurately the signal priorities can reflect the relationship between the signal controllabilities. Note that in the two calculations above, the values of $\text{Prob}\{M_0\}$ and $\text{Prob}\{M_1\}$ do not differ by much.

Let $H(F)_r$ denote the row-reduced $H(F)$. When one performs the calculation of Equation 2.12 with $H(F)_r$ (instead of using $H(F)$), the result will be what we shall refer to as a 1-priority. The 0-priority can be obtained by subtracting the 1-priority from 1. Procedure 3.1 below describes the basic steps for obtaining the signal priorities in a circuit.

Procedure 3.1:

Step 1: With the known probability distribution of fanout input variables, evaluate $\text{Prob}\{M_0\}$ and $\text{Prob}\{M_1\}$.

Step 2: Construct $H(F)_r$ according to following rules:

- a) If $\text{Prob}\{M_0\} > \text{Prob}\{M_1\}$, form $H(F)_r$ by enumerating only fanout input combinations that carry a majority of 0's.

- b) Elseif $\text{Prob}\{M_1\} > \text{Prob}\{M_0\}$, form $H(F)_r$ by enumerating only fanout input combinations that carry a majority of 1's.

- c) Else, form $H(F)_r$ by enumerating only fanout input combinations that carry about the same numbers of 0's and 1's.

Step 3: Use $H(F)_r$ in Step 2 to perform the computation according to Equation 2.12 to obtain the signal priorities for each of the lines in the circuit.

In Procedure 3.1, note that, first, the enumeration process used to construct $H(F)_r$ for all cases in Step 2 is an implicit one.

Second, for all cases in Step 2, the computation of Equation 2.12 (in terms of the number of multiplication and addition) is reduced approximately by half compared to that of the exact method.

It is interesting to note that when each of the elements of matrix $C(1,g)$ in Equation 2.12 is equal to 1, the 1-controllability of g becomes

$$\text{Prob}\{g=1\} = \text{sum}(H(F)_r)$$

where the notation $\text{sum}(A)$ denotes the algebraic sum of all elements of matrix A . Therefore, for a given signal, the maximum difference, Diff_{\max} , between the 1-priority and the exact 1-controllability is

$$\text{Diff}_{\max} = 1 - \text{sum}(H(F)_r) \quad (3.6)$$

As an example, for any signal x in a circuit whose fanout inputs have the probability distributions identical to those in Figure 2, we use Equation 3.6 to compute the maximum difference between the 1-priority and the exact 1-controllability of x to be about 0.16. It is certain that this maximum difference will get smaller as the difference between $\text{Prob}\{M_0\}$ and $\text{Prob}\{M_1\}$ gets larger.

Now, the computation of the signal priorities is demonstrated. In each of the following examples, the signal priorities and the exact signal controllabilities are computed. In these results, for a given signal line, the reader should note the following:

- a) All the time, the 1-priority is smaller compared to the corresponding exact 1-controllability. The maximum difference between the two measures is given in Equation 3.6.

- b) Most of the time, when the 1-priority is higher (lower) than 0.5, the corresponding 1-controllability is also higher (lower) than 0.5.

- c) The 1-priority does not have a significant effect in guiding the test generation process when the corresponding 1-controllability is about 0.5.

Example 3.1: Using Procedure 3.1 above, the 1-priority for every internal line of the circuit in Figure 3 is computed. The results for different randomly generated fanout input probability distributions are shown in Figure 4. Keep in mind that to accelerate a test generation, only signal priorities (not signal controllabilities) are calculated. These values will be used to guide the fault propagation and signal justification processes to prevent the test generation from becoming exhaustive. For

H_i	$F_1 F_2 F_3 F_4 F_5$	$\text{Prob}\{H_i\}$	Notes
H_1	0 0 0 0 0	7.0138836e-005	$\text{Prob}\{F_1=0\}=.5297$ $\text{Prob}\{F_2=0\}=.6711$ $\text{Prob}\{F_3=0\}=.0077$ $\text{Prob}\{F_4=0\}=.3834$ $\text{Prob}\{F_5=0\}=.0668$ $\text{Prob}\{M_0\}=.9117$ $\text{Prob}\{M_1\}=.9999$
H_2	0 0 0 0 1	9.7918026e-004	
H_3	0 0 0 1 0	1.1279276e-004	
H_4	0 0 0 1 1	1.5746546e-003	
H_5	0 0 1 0 0	9.0409471e-003	
H_6	0 0 1 0 1	1.2621705e-001	
H_7	0 0 1 1 0	1.4539069e-002	
H_8	0 0 1 1 1	2.0297413e-001	
H_9	0 1 0 0 0	3.4366715e-005	
H_{10}	0 1 0 0 1	4.7977997e-004	
H_{11}	0 1 0 1 0	5.5266337e-005	
H_{12}	0 1 0 1 1	7.7155124e-004	
H_{13}	0 1 1 0 0	4.4298946e-003	
H_{14}	0 1 1 0 1	6.1843988e-002	
H_{15}	0 1 1 1 0	7.1238711e-003	
H_{16}	0 1 1 1 1	9.9453517e-002	
H_{17}	1 0 0 0 0	6.2273493e-005	
H_{18}	1 0 0 0 1	8.6937534e-004	
H_{19}	1 0 0 1 0	1.0014422e-004	
H_{20}	1 0 0 1 1	1.3980734e-003	
H_{21}	1 0 1 0 0	8.0270986e-003	
H_{22}	1 0 1 0 1	1.1206312e-001	
H_{23}	1 0 1 1 0	1.2908663e-002	
H_{24}	1 0 1 1 1	1.8021268e-001	
H_{25}	1 1 0 0 0	3.0512844e-005	
H_{26}	1 1 0 0 1	4.2597762e-004	
H_{27}	1 1 0 1 0	4.9068790e-005	
H_{28}	1 1 0 1 1	6.8502976e-004	
H_{29}	1 1 1 0 0	3.9331278e-003	
H_{30}	1 1 1 0 1	5.4908826e-002	
H_{31}	1 1 1 1 0	6.3250028e-003	
H_{32}	1 1 1 1 1	8.8300836e-002	

Figure 1. Relationship between $\text{Prob}\{M_v\}$ and $\text{Prob}\{H_i\}$
 $(\text{Prob}\{M_1\} > \text{Prob}\{M_0\})$

H _i	F ₁ F ₂ F ₃ F ₄ F ₅	Prob(H _i)	Notes
H ₁	0 0 0 0 0	8.6095672e-002	Prob{F ₁ =0}= 2470 Prob{F ₂ =0}= 9826 Prob{F ₃ =0}= 7227 Prob{F ₄ =0}= 7534 Prob{F ₅ =0}= 6515 Prob{M ₀ }= 9997 Prob{M ₁ }= 9139
H ₂	0 0 0 0 1	4.6050479e-002	
H ₃	0 0 0 1 0	2.8187205e-002	
H ₄	0 0 0 1 1	1.5076650e-002	
H ₅	0 0 1 0 0	3.3041439e-002	
H ₆	0 0 1 0 1	1.7673061e-002	
H ₇	0 0 1 1 0	1.0817568e-002	
H ₈	0 0 1 1 1	5.7860538e-003	
H ₉	0 1 0 0 0	1.5290259e-003	
H ₁₀	0 1 0 0 1	8.1783873e-004	
H ₁₁	0 1 0 1 0	5.0059388e-004	
H ₁₂	0 1 0 1 1	2.6775548e-004	
H ₁₃	0 1 1 0 0	5.8680319e-004	
H ₁₄	0 1 1 0 1	3.1386674e-004	
H ₁₅	0 1 1 1 0	1.9211583e-004	
H ₁₆	0 1 1 1 1	1.0275808e-004	
H ₁₇	1 0 0 0 0	2.6241494e-001	
H ₁₈	1 0 0 0 1	1.4035936e-001	
H ₁₉	1 0 0 1 0	8.5913070e-002	
H ₂₀	1 0 0 1 1	4.5952810e-002	
H ₂₁	1 0 1 0 0	1.0070851e-001	
H ₂₂	1 0 1 0 1	5.3866531e-002	
H ₂₃	1 0 1 1 0	3.2971360e-002	
H ₂₄	1 0 1 1 1	1.7635578e-002	
H ₂₅	1 1 0 0 0	4.6603880e-003	
H ₂₆	1 1 0 0 1	2.4927281e-003	
H ₂₇	1 1 0 1 0	1.5257830e-003	
H ₂₈	1 1 0 1 1	8.1610416e-004	
H ₂₉	1 1 1 0 0	1.7885443e-003	
H ₃₀	1 1 1 0 1	9.5664880e-004	
H ₃₁	1 1 1 1 0	5.8555863e-004	
H ₃₂	1 1 1 1 1	3.1320106e-004	

Figure 2. Relationship between Prob{M_i} and Prob{H_i}
 (Prob{M₀} > Prob{M₁})

Figure 3. Circuit for Example 3.1

Figure 4. Controllabilities and priorities of Example 3.1; $\text{Prob}\{M0\} > \text{Prob}\{M1\}$;
 $\text{Prob}\{M0\}=0.9997$, $\text{Prob}\{M1\}=0.9139$, $\text{Prob}\{F1=0\}=0.247$,
 $\text{Prob}\{F2=0\}=0.9826$, $\text{Prob}\{F3=0\}=0.7227$, $\text{Prob}\{F4=0\}=0.7537$,
 $\text{Prob}\{F5=0\}=0.651$

instance, if $t_{12}=0$ in Figure 3 is to be justified, one has two choices for (t_5, t_{10}) . They are $(0, 0)$ and $(1, 1)$. In this case, and if the test generator is set up to examine the inputs of a logic gate based on a top-down procedure (i.e., the input signal located on the topmost of the schematic of a logic gate is examined first), and if the signal priority values shown in Figure 4 is used, $t_5=1$ will be chosen because the 1-priority of t_5 is higher than 0.5.

Example 3.2: This example is for a part of an actual circuit that is now maintained at the Oklahoma City Air Logistics Center, Tinker Air Force Base. The circuit has 7 fanout input variables (see Figure 5). The simulated results are shown in Figure 6. Note that, occasionally, the difference between the 1-priority and the 1-controllability of a given line is so small that it cannot be shown clearly on a graph. This is the case for signals t_6, t_{23} of Figure 6.

Example 3.3: To show additional detail on how the signal priorities are used to accelerate the test generation, the D-algorithm [Roth 1966] was used to detect the sa1 fault on line t_{13} of the circuit in Example 3.1. In this test pattern generation example, there are three cases to be considered:

a) The test generation is performed without using the signal priorities. The backtracking effort in this case depends on the topology of the circuit.

b) The test generation is guided by at least one signal priority that incorrectly predicts the exact controllability. The line t_5 is arbitrarily chosen as a test case in this example. The backtracking effort in this case is expected to be exhaustive.

c) The test generation is guided by at least one signal priority that correctly predicts the exact controllability. As in Case b, the line t_5 is arbitrarily chosen as a test case. Compared to the other two cases, the backtracking effort in this case is expected to be minimum.

In all cases, first, the backtracking effort made by the test generator is described in terms of the number of the combinations of all signal lines that the test generator tries before it finds a primary input combination for detecting the fault. Second, the signal priority values shown in Figure 4 will be used.

Case a: The test generation is performed without using the priority, i.e., there is no guidance. The test generator first sets line t_{13} to 0, then performs the signal justification toward the circuit's inputs. When a conflict is found, the test generator backtracks toward the output of the circuit to reselect different values to resolve the conflict. The process continues until the test pattern that can set line t_{13} to 0 is found. The desired test pattern is $(f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5, p_1, p_2, p_3) = (1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1)$. The total number of all-signal combinations the test generator tries before this valid input test pattern is found is 298. This number depends on the topology of the circuit.

Case b: In this case, t_5 will be set to a fixed value to guide the test generation. Suppose that, for some

reason, the priority incorrectly predicts the exact 1-controllability of line t_5 . Instead of using $t_5=1$, the test generator uses $t_5=0$ to guide the search. The result is that the test generation degenerates into an exhaustive process, and finds no input pattern for detecting the sa1 fault on line t_{13} . For this test generation, the total number of all-signal combinations that the test generator tries is 576. After finding no input pattern to detect the fault on line t_{13} , the test generator, by default, will have to backtrack, switch t_5 to 1, and resume the test generation.

Case c: In this case, the test generator uses $t_5=1$ according to the value in Figure 4. Since the test generation is correctly guided this time, the total number of all-signal combinations that the generator tries is 11. This number is the smallest compared to the other two cases. The input test pattern required to detect the fault is the same as that of Case a.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this research, we introduced signal priorities to guide the test generation process and demonstrated that the computation process is greatly reduced over previous methods involving signal controllabilities.

We employed the minimum-value distributions of the fan-out input variables of the circuit to achieve the significant reduction in the computation effort. Then based on these distributions, we enumerated only those test patterns which contributed a significant weight to the computation of the signal controllability of a circuit line. The signal priority was the result of this implicit computation process.

We showed that this implicit method reduced the amount of computation for the signal priority of a given line in a circuit by about half compared to the exact signal controllability. We also demonstrated that the overall DATPG was significantly accelerated by using the signal priorities. A method for evaluating the maximum difference between the 1-priority and the exact 1-controllability for any given signal in a circuit was also presented.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors express appreciation to David R. Corder, John D. Holcomb and Thomas Saunkeah of the Software Division, Tinker AFB, and Dr. Imadeddine Abouzahr of Oklahoma State University for their support on this project.

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Figure 5. Circuit for Example 3.2

Figure 6. Controllabilities and priorities of Example 3.2; $\text{Prob}\{M0\} < \text{Prob}\{M1\}$;
 $\text{Prob}\{M0\}=0.9854$, $\text{Prob}\{M1\}=1$, $\text{Prob}\{F1=0\}=0.831$, $\text{Prob}\{F2=0\}=0.0346$,
 $\text{Prob}\{F3=0\}=0.0535$, $\text{Prob}\{F4=0\}=0.5297$, $\text{Prob}\{F5=0\}=0.6711$,
 $\text{Prob}\{F6=0\}=0.0077$, $\text{Prob}\{F7=0\}=0.3834$

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